

Impact of Interfaces and Laser Repetition Rate on Photocarrier Dynamics in Lead Halide Perovskites

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ABSTRACT

We studied charge carrier recombination in methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) perovskite and the impact of interfaces on the charge carrier lifetime using time-resolved photoluminescence. Pristine films and those covered with organic electron and hole transport materials (TM) were investigated at various laser repetition rates ranging from 10 kHz to 10 MHz in order to separate the bulk and interface-affected recombination. We revealed two different components in the PL decay. The fast component (shorter than 300 ns) is assigned to interfacial processes, and the slow one to bulk recombination. A high repetition pulse train was shown to shorten PL decay in pristine perovskite, while significantly prolonging the photocarrier lifetime in MAPbI₃ covered by TMs. This effect can be qualitatively explained with kinetic model taking interface traps into account. We demonstrate a significant influence of excitation repetition rate on photocarrier lifetime, which should be considered when studying charge carrier dynamics in perovskites.

TOC GRAPHICS

Hybrid halide perovskite-based photovoltaics have sustained dramatic development over the past years, achieving solar cells with power conversion efficiencies above 22%.¹ This tremendous efficiency progress can be attributed to the appealing intrinsic properties of the lead-based (bulk) perovskites themselves, such as long charge-carrier lifetimes,²⁻⁴ low exciton binding energy,⁵ and high absorption coefficient (10^4 – 10^5 cm⁻¹ in the visible region),^{6,7} as well as the film quality of the perovskite absorber,^{8,9} development of energetically suitable charge transport materials,¹⁰ and variation of device architecture.¹¹ Despite the great efficiency progress, the unintentional defects formed during growth should be seriously considered due to their impact on charge carrier recombination,¹² and generally on the charge transport properties, which inhibits the targeted production of high-performance solar cells. Scientific discussions about trap origins, their energetics in perovskites, and their impact on solar cell performance remains ongoing.

The adjacent charge transport layers in a solar cell are of particular importance due to the assumed defect tolerance of halide perovskites.^{13,14} They not only determine the growing conditions and the crystallinity of the perovskite film, but also form interfaces, which can in turn lead to losses of photogenerated charge carriers. Therefore, the separation of bulk and interface recombination effects is non-trivial, and combined measurements on incomplete devices as well as on pristine films are necessary. Steady-state (PL) and time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) are widely used non-contact characterisation techniques for semiconductors. PL signal, being proportional to the density product of recombining electrons and holes, is sensitive to a variety of processes that change the excited state population.¹⁵ Coexistence of several recombination pathways – including trap-assisted first order, band-to-band second order and higher order Auger recombination^{15,16} – results in different decay dynamics and makes exponential fits hardly justifiable or alternatively requires the numerical analysis of PL transients with a number of characteristic constants.⁴ It

leads to ambiguity in interpretation of TRPL data and discrepancies among the published recombination models.^{4,16–18} Note that nearly all recombination models include trap-assisted processes. Trap filling and depopulation are anticipated to be of crucial importance for the interpretation of carrier dynamics in perovskites. By depositing quenching layers on perovskites² and combining one- and two-photon fluorescence microscopy, a separation of surface and bulk effects due to different penetration depths of blue and red light in the mixed halide perovskites structures was possible.¹⁹

The role of repetition rate in the TRPL experiment and its impact on recombination dynamics has not previously been addressed. Usually, the repetition rate is fixed to a certain value between 100 kHz and 80 MHz, depending on the laser system. Here we show that one can pile-up charge carriers and therefore greatly influence the carrier dynamics in perovskites by varying the laser repetition rate, f , in the TRPL experiment. A similar approach was used by *M. Saba et al.* to investigate photoluminescence dynamics in colloidal core-shell nanocrystals.²⁰ Both photocharging and charge trapping were found to contribute to photoluminescence quenching.

In this manuscript, we studied methylammonium lead iodide ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$) perovskite films formed on a glass substrate and then divided into four parts. Electron or hole transport materials (ETM or HTM) were subsequently spin-coated on top of the samples. With an ETM/HTM present we observe significant prolongation of PL lifetime with increasing f , in spite of a possible formation of extrinsic defects at the interface. We explain such behaviour with a quasi-stationary charge carrier population built-up at higher f , and effective filling of the interfacial traps, which leads to their passivation. We discuss the impact of f on radiative emission decay in the framework of commonly used kinetic models. Here we highlight the role of the interfaces between the lead halide perovskite and the various charge transport

materials. Our results illustrate the impact of the interfaces on recombination and demonstrate how the interface trap filling leads to prolongation of apparent charge carrier lifetime.

We studied $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ films (further referred to as MAPbI_3) covered with charge transport materials widely implemented in perovskite photovoltaics: PC_{60}BM (ETM), P3HT (HTM) and Spiro-MeOTAD (HTM). MAPbI_3 film was formed on a 1x1 sq.-inch pre-cut glass substrate and then separated into four parts. Charge transport materials were then spin-coated on top of three of them (see **Figure 1(a)** and Experimental Section), while the fourth sample, a pristine MAPbI_3 film, was used as a reference. With this approach, we attempted to maintain the same crystallization conditions for the perovskite film in all studied samples and to isolate the influences of the interfaces between MAPbI_3 and the transport layers. Note that an interface between bulk MAPbI_3 and air-exposed MAPbI_3 can also occur in the non-encapsulated reference sample.

Figure 1(b) shows normalized PL transients for pristine MAPbI_3 and MAPbI_3 with charge transport layers. PL was excited at 505 nm and collected from the top of every sample, i.e. through the transport layers in layered films. All transients were detected at the maximum of perovskite emission, 770 nm (see steady-state PL spectra in **Figure S1**). The unchanged PL band of MAPbI_3 in all steady-state spectra indicates that the perovskite electronic structure is also maintained for samples with additional charge-selective layers.

PL spectra, absolute intensity and normalized transients in pristine uncovered MAPbI_3 films (see Figure S6) do not change within 1 hour under illumination (the total measurement time for each sample, see Experimental Methods). Therefore we do not consider here perovskite damage. PL from Spiro-MeOTAD and PC_{60}BM does not overlap with the relevant region of perovskite emission. The P3HT layer shows weak PL emission at 770 nm, but it decays within 1 ns (see **Figure S2**), which is below the time resolution of the setup (see instrument

response function in **Figure S3**). Therefore, the excitation and detection through charge transport layers should not affect the PL transients significantly.

All four measured PL transients show an initial fast decay and an extended, slower decay. Thereby, the charge transport layers noticeably change the relative magnitudes of the fast and slow portions in the recombination dynamics. PL transient decays much faster in the presence of the electron-selective PC₆₀BM layer, and PL becomes almost negligible after 300 ns. Meantime, a slow PL component dominates in the samples with hole-selective layers – Spiro-MeOTAD and P3HT.

Figure 1(c) shows the same PL transients, normalized to the slower decay portion of the reference sample MAPbI₃. The plot allows temporal separation of the two sections in the PL transient: the fast part, in which PL decay differs depending on the different interfaces, extends up to 300 ns, while the slower portion is exactly the same for all four investigated samples. The perovskite film morphology is expected to be identical for all examined samples due to the same growing conditions, so we ascribe the slow PL decay to bulk recombination and the initial fast decay to interface-affected recombination.

Figure 1. (a) Scheme of sample preparation. MAPbI₃ film (black) was prepared on a 1x1 sq.-inch glass substrate and then cut into four parts. Charge-selective layers (PC₆₀BM (green), Spiro-MeOTAD (red) and P3HT (blue)) were deposited on top of three of them. (b-c) PL decays in the perovskite films recorded under ambient conditions at 770 nm with pulsed-laser excitation at 505 nm, and laser repetition rate $f = 1$ MHz. The transients are normalized to the initial PL peak in (b) and to the slower decay portion of the reference MAPbI₃ sample in (c).

The laser repetition rate in the TRPL experiment is an important parameter that must be individually chosen for any system under study. The time lag between two subsequent

excitation pulses should usually exceed the relaxation time of the excited state. This condition ensures that excitation of the unrelaxed system to higher energy levels is avoided, simplifying data interpretation.²¹ Additionally, the pulse train with high repetition rate may pile-up the charge carrier density in the sample and lead to shorter PL lifetimes in the case of second order recombination.

Figure 2 shows normalized PL transients taken at different rates f for every sample. Position of the sample, monochromator bandwidths, excitation beam focus, laser pulse energy and other parameters besides the laser repetition rate were fixed for all experiments presented here. Transients in every set were taken from the slowest to the fastest laser repetition rate.

Figure 2 clearly demonstrates a strong influence of the laser repetition rate on the PL decay in all samples. It implies the existence of an optimal, sufficiently low repetition rate, f , for each individual perovskite system. Above this threshold, f begins to affect the PL decay. In other words, the repetition rate should be taken into account as a parameter influencing carrier recombination dynamics in perovskites.

Figure 2. Normalized PL decays taken at various f values (excitation at 505 nm, detection at 770 nm). (a) – pristine MAPbI₃, (b) – MAPbI₃ with electron-selective layer PC₆₀BM, (c) – MAPbI₃ with hole-selective layer P3HT, (d) – MAPbI₃ with hole-selective layer Spiro-MeOTAD. Dots represent the experimental data; black curves show numerical fits for MAPbI₃ to the kinetic model of Equations 1-3. Colour coding of the experimental points corresponds to f (see the legend in (b)).

Figure 3 demonstrates a qualitative difference between bulk recombination (pristine MAPbI₃) and interface-affected recombination (MAPbI₃ with charge-selective layers) in the PL transients. Since the transient curves cannot be fully described by an analytical function, we choose an arbitrary level, I_0 , that defines the characteristic time, τ_0 , which is taken as the time necessary for the normalized PL transients to decay to the level I_0 (as assigned in **Figure 2(a)**). Remarkably, τ_0 demonstrates an opposite behaviour for the reference (pristine) MAPbI₃ film compared to MAPbI₃ with charge transport materials. In the case of bulk recombination

(pristine MAPbI₃), PL lifetime decreases with rising f , while in the case of interface-affected recombination (MAPbI₃ with transport materials) an increase of PL decay is revealed.

Figure 3. Characteristic PL lifetime τ_0 versus laser repetition rate f . τ_0 is taken as the time necessary for the normalized PL transients to decay to the arbitrary level I_0 (see **Figure 2** (a)), which is the same for all investigated samples.

The effect of repetition rate f on recombination dynamics of charge carriers is schematically explained in **Figure 4**. If f is low enough, most of the photogenerated charge carriers recombine before the consecutive laser pulse. As frequency increases, a background population of charge carriers will built-up and trap-state filling will occur. The excess of background carriers will accelerate band-to-band recombination, because the probability to recombine is directly proportional to the product of charge-carrier density. Simultaneously, interfacial traps remain filled making subsequent electron capture ineffective.

PL in MAPbI₃ at room temperature arises from direct band-to-band recombination of electrons and holes. A slower electron-hole recombination via indirect transition in MAPbI₃ was also proposed recently.^{22,23} So long as the temperature remains constant, there is no

mathematical difference between electron release via trap depopulation or indirect transition, therefore we neglect the latter.

Now we consider charge carrier recombination in the framework of a kinetic model, including direct band-to-band recombination, electron trapping, trap depopulation via electron-hole recombination and electron release from the traps to the conduction band.^{4,17,24} Each of these processes is proportional to the charge carrier density with characteristic rate constants, as denoted in Equations (1-3):

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = -R_{np}np - R_{tr}n(N_T - n_T) + R_{rel}n_T \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dn_T(t)}{dt} = R_{tr}n(N_T - n_T) - R_{dep}n_Tp - R_{rel}n_T \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dp(t)}{dt} = -R_{np}np - R_{dep}n_Tp. \quad (3)$$

Here n is the density of photoexcited electrons in the conduction band, p is the density of photoexcited holes in the valence band, n_T is the density of trapped electrons, and N_T is the constant density of traps in the perovskite film. R_{np} , R_{tr} , R_{dep} and R_{rel} are the characteristic rates of band-to-band recombination, electron trapping, trap depopulation via electron-hole recombination and electron release, respectively (see **Figure 4**). One can also include hole-trapping in the model, which will not change the resulting fits qualitatively, but will increase the number of parameters (see **Figure S7** and **Equations S1-S4**). For the sake of simplicity, we do not consider the hole trapping here.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of photocarrier dynamics within the regimes of low (a) and high (b) laser repetition rates f . (b) At higher f , the PL decay is incomplete (red line) and the residual population of photocarriers builds up. The conduction band and traps are partially filled by the arrival of the consecutive laser pulse. Traps are shown as a single energy level for simplicity.

Effect of laser repetition rate can be included in the model through the initial conditions for charge carrier densities: $n(0) = n_{inj} + n_0$; $p(0) = p_{inj} + p_0$; $n_T(0) = n_{T0}$. Here, $n_{inj} = p_{inj} = const$ are densities of electrons and holes generated with a single laser pulse; n_0 , p_0 and n_{T0} are the excess of free and trapped carrier populations built up by the previous laser pulses. In the case of bulk recombination – when no interface states are involved – much faster PL decay with f can be attributed to the term $R_{np}np$ (Equations (1,3)). Both n and p increase with f , so their product increases accordingly and the excited state depopulation occurs faster.

In case of interface-affected recombination, the slowing down of the PL decay with rising f is related to the interfacial trap-filling, which reduces the number of unoccupied trap states, i.e. $(N_T - n_T) \rightarrow 0$ in the case of trapped electrons. As a result, both interfacial charge trapping and interface-assisted recombination become less probable with increasing f , and the bulk interface-free transient is restored.

Experimental transients for pristine MAPbI₃ were numerically modelled with the kinetic Equations (1-3) (see solid lines in **Figure 2(a)** and **Figure S4**). All characteristic constants, namely R_{np} , N_T , R_{tr} , R_{rel} , and R_{dep} , were extracted from the fit of the PL decay at the lowest $f = 0.1$ MHz and kept constant during the modelling at higher repetition rates. Thus any transient variations at higher f can be attributed to the change of excess carrier densities n_0 , p_0 and n_{T0} .

The values of characteristic rates and trap densities deduced from the numerical fit of TRPL in **Figure 2(a)** are $R_{np} \sim 10^{-9}$ cm³ s⁻¹, $N_T \sim 10^{15}$ cm⁻³. However, we would like to emphasise that the PL transients can also be modelled with another set of parameters (see **Figure S5**). Trap depopulation can be excluded from the model ($R_{dep} = 0$) without apparent effect on PL transients (see **Figure S5** and **Figure 5**). Some of the parameters, e.g. R_{np} and n_0 ; R_{tr} and N_T , appear in Equations (1-3) as a product. These parameters are not mathematically independent and thus cannot be extracted separately. Additional processes, which we do not consider here, should be taken into account by modelling the transient PL in the case of MAPbI₃ with transport layers (see **Figure S7** and **Equations S1-S4**).²⁵ However, with the simplified set of kinetic Equations (1-3), all major features and tendencies of PL transients, such as the fast and slow decay or the effects of repetition rate, can be qualitatively explained by solely varying the trap density N_T (see **Figure 5**).

	$R_{np}, \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$	N_T, cm^{-3}	$R_{tr}, \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$	R_{rel}, s^{-1}	$R_{dep}, \text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
(a)	4.0×10^{-9}	1.0×10^{15}	2.0×10^{-9}	2.8×10^6	0
(b)	4.0×10^{-9}	5.0×10^{16}	2.0×10^{-9}	2.8×10^6	0

Figure 5. Graph modelling the effect of pulse repetition rate on charge carrier dynamics. Transients (a) and (b) are calculated accordingly to the kinetic model (Equations (1-3)) with the same set of parameters besides the number of electron traps N_T (see table).

In this work, we investigated the effect of laser repetition rate on charge carrier recombination dynamics in methylammonium lead-iodide perovskite films. The TRPL technique was used to study the charge carrier recombination in both pristine MAPbI₃ films and MAPbI₃ films with organic ETM or HTM on top, namely PC₆₀BM, Spiro-MeOTAD and P3HT. Bulk- and interface-affected recombination was separated in our TRPL experiment. The fast component of PL decay (up to 300 ns) is assigned to interfacial processes and the slower one to bulk perovskite recombination. Laser repetition rate was shown to shorten PL decay in pristine perovskite, while significantly prolonging the charge carrier lifetime in MAPbI₃ with additional interfaces. We qualitatively explained this effect in the frame of a commonly used kinetic model. It was demonstrated that the PL lifetime in a broad range can be obtained for the same sample by optical trap-filling. This study emphasizes the significant influence of laser repetition rate on charge carrier lifetime, which should be taken into account when studying charge carrier recombination dynamics in perovskites.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Sample preparation

A perovskite layer was processed on a 1x1 sq.-inch glass substrate without any modifications. This substrate was cleaned in a sequence of deionized water, acetone and isopropanol for 10 min each in an ultrasonic bath before use. Perovskite film was synthesized with a two-step interdiffusion process.²⁶ In the first step, we used a 400 mg/ml PbI_2 solution (n,n-dimethylformamide) with a small amount of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$ (molar ratio of 0.2 in reference to PbI_2). After spin-coating, the substrate was annealed for 15 minutes at 70°C . Afterwards, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{I}$ (40 mg/ml dissolved in 2-propanol) was spin-coated and heated at 100°C for 60 minutes in a DMSO atmosphere to form the perovskite layer. After cooling down to room temperature, the substrate was broken into 4 parts. One part was used without any further preparation as a reference, while the other substrates were covered with different charge transport materials, commonly used in planar and mesoporous perovskite solar cells. PC_{60}BM was used as the ETM. It was spin-coated using a 20 mg/ml 1,2-dichlorobenzene solution, followed by annealing for 60 minutes at 100°C . The third perovskite film was covered with Spiro-MeOTAD (80mg/ml in chlorobenzene doped with bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide in acetonitrile, tert-butylpyridine and FK209 (tris(2-(1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-4-tert-butylpyridine)-cobalt(III) tris(bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide) in acetonitrile) according to the procedure described elsewhere.²⁷ The last sample was spin-coated with P3HT dissolved in chlorobenzene with a concentration of 15 mg/ml and an annealing time of 5 min at 100°C .

PL measurements

PL and transient PL were measured with calibrated Fluorescence Spectrometer FLS980-s (Edinburgh Instruments), equipped with two excitation sources: continuous broad-spectrum xenon lamp Xe1 and pulsed green laser EPL-510 (wavelength 505.2 nm, pulse width 105 ps). Laser repetition rate was tuneable with discrete steps ranging from 10 kHz to 10 MHz. Laser

pulse fluence was 7.6 nJ/cm^2 , which corresponds to photogenerated carrier density of $2.0 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the given wavelength in MAPbI₃ film. During the PL measurements, samples were exposed to the ambient air and 40% humidity at room temperature. Acquisition time for every transient presented was 10 minutes. Thus the total measurement time for every sample did not exceed 1 hour.

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ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Steady-state PL spectra of pristine MAPbI₃ and MAPbI₃ with charge selective layers, PL transients of P3HT film, instrument response function for TRPL measurements, normalized PL decays taken at different laser repetition rates in pristine MAPbI₃, numerical fits with three different set of parameters for PL decay in pristine MAPbI₃ and the steady-state and transient PL spectra on uncovered MAPbI₃ taken before and after measurements.

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